

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI
VAZIRLAR MAHKAMASI HUZURIDAGI
BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK OLIY MAKTABI

IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT
Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Yashil

Barqarorlik uchun innovatsiyalar:

Yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish davrida
biznes va tadbirkorlik bo'yicha

2025 - yil
1-30-aprel

RESEARCH
AND GRANTS UPDATES

NAVBATDAN
TASHQARI SON

<https://gsbe-research.uz/conferences-ups-uz>

conference@gsbe.uz

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi

Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayeich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati

Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari

Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor

Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)

Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)

Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari

Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i

Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.

Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)

Krissi Luis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)

Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari

Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

*Elektron nashr. 133 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-iyunda ruxsat etildi.*

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.11 Marketing
08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
08.00.13 Menejment
08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Dunyo sug'urta bozorida yashil xizmatlarning taraqqiyot strategiyalari.....	7
Alimov Baxodir Batirovich	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida amaliy va nazariy treninglar orqali xususiy tadbirkorlik faoliyatining samaradorligini oshirish.....	14
Marupov Kabil Komilovich	
O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotini yashillashtirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning joriy holati tahlili.....	20
Nurmetova Muyassar	
Econometric assessment of the impact of investments on the economic system of Surkhandarya region	29
Nurbek Khatamov	
Debt versus tax financing in infrastructure: impact on employment	37
Raxmatov Firdavs Feruz o'g'li, Kengesbaeva Gulfayruz Azamatovna	
Digital infrastructure and green energy in export diversification: evidence from post-soviet countries.....	47
Sadriddinov Ulugbek Jaloliddin ugli	
Jahon savdo tashkiloti doirasida O'zbekistonning iqtisodiy rivojlanish istiqbollari: ko'p tomonlama savdo kelishuvlari tahlili	55
Toshpulatova Malika Ulug'bek qizi	
Развитие финтеха в узбекистане: современное состояние и международный контекст	63
Адилова Сакинахон	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni innovasion rivojlantirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash	68
Rasulova Dilfuza, Kaytarov Voxid	
Gibrid avtomobillar importida to'lovlar undirish amaliyotini takomillashtirish.....	80
Kaljanov Baxadir Dauletbaevich	
Стратегии корпоративного управления и привлечения иностранных инвестиций в условиях устойчивой экономики.....	88
Фарход Каракулов	
The impact of WTO accession on Uzbekistan's trade policy: in the case of Kazakhstan	102
Azimjonov Muhammadsoli Muhammadolim o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda aholi turmush darajasini oshirishda davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlari va mexanizmlari	110
Xolto'rayev Islom Ilhomovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA BARQAROR BIZNES MODELLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA INNOVATSIYALARNING ROLI	113
Otaboyev Axmed Maxsudbek o'g'li, Raxmatullayev Sardor Afzal o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KORPORATIV MOLIYA BOSHQARUVINI KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPI) VOSITASIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	116
Jumatova Gulzar Maxmud qizi	
TURIZM SOHASIDA MEHMONXONA XIZMATLARNING MILLIY TURIZM IQTISODIYOTIDAGI FUNKSIYASI VA XUSUSIYATLARI	119
Mir-Jafarova Aziza Javoxirovna	
ISTE'MOLCHI XULQ-ATVORI VA BRENDA ASOSIDA CHAKANA SAVDO RIVOJLANISHINING STRATEGIK ASOSLARI.....	124
Ro'zimatov Shohboz Hamdambek o'g'li	
INVESTITSIYA MUHITINING JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH ZARURATI, BELGILOVCHI OMILLARI VA O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	129
U.N.Muxammadiyev	
THE ROLE AND DIRECTIONS OF STATE POLICY IN ENSURING MACROECONOMIC STABILITY	131
Suvonov Tolmasjon Faxritdinovich	

THE ROLE AND DIRECTIONS OF STATE POLICY IN ENSURING MACROECONOMIC STABILITY

Suvonov Tolmasjon Faxritdinovich

Tashkent State University of Economics

tolmasjon1212@gmail.com

Abstract: This thesis analyzes the role, objectives, and main directions of state policy in ensuring macroeconomic stability. The study examines monetary policy, fiscal policy, economic diversification, social protection systems, and their interaction in maintaining economic stability.

Key words: state policy, macroeconomic stability, monetary policy, fiscal policy, economic diversification, social protection.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda davlat siyosatining o'ri, vazifalari va asosiy yo'nalishlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda monetar siyosat, fiskal siyosat, iqtisodiy diversifikatsiya, ijtimoiy himoya tizimlari hamda ularning barqarorlikni ta'minlashdagi o'zaro ta'siri o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat siyosati, makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik, monetar siyosat, fiskal siyosat, iqtisodiy diversifikatsiya, ijtimoiy himoya.

Аннотация: В данном тезисе анализируются роль, задачи и основные направления государственной политики в обеспечении макроэкономической стабильности. В исследовании рассматриваются монетарная политика, фискальная политика, экономическая диверсификация, системы социальной защиты, а также их взаимное влияние на обеспечение стабильности.

Ключевые слова: государственная политика, макроэкономическая стабильность, монетарная политика, фискальная политика, экономическая диверсификация, социальная защита.

INTRODUCTION

Macroeconomic stability is considered one of the main conditions for the long-term and sustainable development of any country. It includes price stability, exchange rate stability, continuity of economic growth, and a high level of employment. In this process, state policy plays a decisive and coordinating role.

The state's responsibilities in ensuring macroeconomic stability are implemented through various policy instruments. These include monetary policy, fiscal policy, financial regulation, economic diversification, social protection systems, and foreign economic policy. Effective coordination among these policy directions serves as an important foundation for maintaining economic stability.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been carrying out large-scale reforms aimed at strengthening macroeconomic stability. In particular, stability is being reinforced through increasing the independence of the Central Bank, improving the tax system, optimizing the state budget, promoting economic diversification, and expanding the social protection system.

In studying the relationship between state policy and macroeconomic stability, John Maynard Keynes established an important theoretical foundation. In his General Theory, he substantiated the necessity of state intervention in economic processes and proposed supporting aggregate demand through increased government spending during periods of economic slowdown. According to Keynes, market mechanisms alone may not always ensure stability, and therefore state intervention can play an important stabilizing role.

Milton Friedman and Anna Schwartz conducted significant research on monetary policy and inflation control. In their works, they analyzed the influence of the money supply on macroeconomic indicators and emphasized the importance of an independent monetary policy conducted by central banks. An independent central bank can contribute effectively to maintaining price stability and controlling inflationary pressures.

Alberto Alesina also produced important scientific works on the relationship between fiscal policy and economic stability. His studies examined the impact of public debt on economic growth and demonstrated that maintaining budget discipline and improving the efficiency of government expenditures contribute positively to macroeconomic stability.

World Bank and United Nations play an important role in studying economic diversification and stability issues. These organizations recommend that countries diversify their economies, support the development of multiple sectors, and strengthen domestic markets to improve resilience against external shocks.

Issues related to improving state policy and ensuring macroeconomic stability in Uzbekistan are also being actively studied by local researchers. Their studies emphasize the importance of economic diversification, tax system reforms, budget policy optimization, and the development of social protection systems in strengthening economic stability.

The role of state policy in ensuring macroeconomic stability is reflected in several key directions. First, through monetary policy, the Central Bank regulates inflation, manages the money supply, and supports exchange rate stability. Second, through fiscal policy, the state stimulates economic growth, promotes social welfare, and maintains budgetary balance (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Evaluation of the effectiveness of state policy directions¹

Third, through economic diversification policy, the state expands export opportunities, supports the balanced development of import and domestic production processes, promotes the growth of new industries, and strengthens a competitive market environment. These measures contribute to increasing economic resilience and creating broader opportunities for sustainable growth.

Fourth, through the social protection system, the state supports vulnerable segments of the population, contributes to poverty reduction, and promotes social stability. Strengthening social support mechanisms and improving living standards play an important role in maintaining overall macroeconomic stability and ensuring inclusive economic development (Figure 2).

Figure 2. GDP growth and unemployment dynamics (Uzbekistan, 2020-2024)²

1 author's development
2 author's development

In Uzbekistan, effective policy measures should continue to be implemented in several key directions to ensure macroeconomic stability.

First, it is important to further strengthen the independence of the Central Bank and enhance the transparency of monetary policy. These measures can contribute to maintaining price stability, improving market confidence, and increasing the effectiveness of inflation management.

Second, efforts should continue toward making the tax system more fair, efficient, and transparent, while reducing tax evasion and broadening the tax base. Improving tax administration can support stable budget revenues and create a more favorable business environment.

Third, it is important to optimize state expenditures, strengthen oversight of subsidies, and increase the efficiency of infrastructure projects. Enhancing the effectiveness of public spending can contribute to sustainable economic growth, better resource allocation, and stronger macroeconomic stability.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study analyzed the role and main directions of state policy in ensuring macroeconomic stability. The analysis showed that the state's role in maintaining macroeconomic stability is important and multifaceted. Monetary policy, fiscal policy, economic diversification, and the social protection system serve as the main pillars of economic stability.

The economy of Uzbekistan has achieved significant progress in recent years. At the same time, global risks and internal structural challenges require consistent efforts to preserve and strengthen stability. Long-term macroeconomic stability can be achieved through economic diversification, improved public administration, effective fiscal and monetary coordination, and the promotion of social equity.

Future research should focus more deeply on models for evaluating the effectiveness of state policy, mechanisms for coordinating different policy directions, and innovative approaches to ensuring sustainable economic stability.

REFERENCES

1. John Maynard Keynes (1936). *The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money*. London: Macmillan.
2. Milton Friedman, & Anna Schwartz (1963). *A Monetary History of the United States*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
3. Alberto Alesina (2010). *Fiscal Adjustments: Lessons from Recent History*. Harvard University Working Paper.
4. World Bank (2023). *World Development Report*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
5. Government of Uzbekistan. *Economic Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan*. – Tashkent, 2024.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025-yil. navbatdan tashqari son

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

